
Nonagon Leadership Grid

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ABSTRACT

Leadership is not about a good leader or a bad leader, it's about understanding the functioning of the system of heart and mind aligned to decide excellence with love, care and kindness with firm perseverance to positive outcomes. This paper intends to explain that Leadership is a strong word by its pronunciation and its essence of existence in every heart and mind encourages to transform themselves and others at each step of life.

KEYWORDS: Leadership, Empathy, Decision making, Locus of control.

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